

THE ROLE OF PRINCIPLES AND METHODS IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract: This article discusses the characteristics of the principles and methods of teaching English in today's educational system. Also, information about the mechanism of educational methods in the process of teaching English is described.

Key words: functional process, intellectual aspect, professional efficiency, method, method, principles.

Nowadays, the use of modern pedagogical technologies in the teaching and learning of the English language is developing consistently and sustainably in all educational institutions, as well as being implemented on a large scale. As a result, the variety of training rooms in all educational institutions is increasing, creating rich opportunities for students and students, as well as opening wide opportunities for effective teaching and learning. As the number of English language learners around the world is increasing day by day, there is an important issue, the existing resource centers in all educational institutions require the formation of a resource that covers the necessary guide materials for learners based on modern methods. Undoubtedly, it is important in the scientific organization of the lesson, as well as the creation of an immovable strategic foundation template is the need of the hour, which, in turn, is divided into several principles and methods. The purpose of this is to focus on increasing the effectiveness of the lesson.

The educational process conducted by pedagogues-teachers in the training laboratory with the participation of students based on modern educational methods is a source of cooperation based on two partnerships, and the realization of the expected result in the final part determines the creativity skills of the teacher. A different approach to training is aimed not only at strengthening the thinking capacity, but also at the sharp development of the student's skills related to the field (speaking, writing, reading, listening). The interlinking of interactive methods with skills is explained by the interesting and complementary nature of the lessons. Ensuring its continuity undoubtedly requires a responsible and skillful approach of pedagogues to their task.

In today's modern era, we see classroom activities with a creative approach and teaching. In determining the knowledge, abilities, and skills of pedagogues-teachers, the effectiveness of the principles or the chosen method in each lesson is determined based on the end of the lesson and the performance of the students during the lesson. So, it is clear from this that it is not limited to the application and

introduction of modern pedagogical technologies, but to clearly indicate the purpose of the method, the used method, and the principles in increasing the effectiveness of education. If we look at the content and classification of teaching methods and principles, they are explained as follows:

The principle of teaching.

It is the collective sum total of ideas, beliefs, and methods of natural learning in the classroom.

Teaching strategy.

A clear teaching pattern to achieve the intended goal by considering a comprehensive term plan.

Teaching method.

A systematic way of doing something. A step-by-step approach to a logical plan. A very effective method. The teaching technique is a creative approach based on a well-defined routine of special activity and task implementation.

The principle of separate engagement.

In this, the student is required to work separately and alone, the goal is for the student to be able to solve the problem situation independently.

The principle of accurate teaching

Here it is clearly interpreted from the teacher to tell and show or demonstrate.

An orderly principle.

It is limited, the discussion of the teacher is based on the intended topic with the participation of students.

The principle of cooperation.

Group, team, partnership work and group discussion; relies on a collaborative approach.

Interactive principle.

In this principle, in an interactive classroom, more students speak and the role of the teacher is less. Students are allowed to interact with the teacher and other students.

The principle of creative device.

"Creating students' knowledge skills and understanding the essence of pre-existing skills experience".

The principle and method of the educational strategy mentioned above is a set of general educational components. "These components strengthen the overall integration process in English language teaching, and as a result, gradually develop the teaching and learning procedures."¹. When determining the professional

¹ O'.Hoshimov, I.Yoqubov. Ingliz tilini o'qitish metodikasi (o'quv qo'llanma) T.-.,Sharq Nashriyoti.2013

component skill of each teacher in teaching English, it is determined by his ability to organize the training, the structural strategic principle, and the method principle that can effectively perform the sequential steps. Therefore, there are several principles in the organization of a high-quality lesson, which in their place are the full achievement of the intended goal of the teacher and students. It is definitely impossible to use several methods during training, or to use at least one method in full efficiency is undoubtedly a complicated process. Accordingly, we cannot say which method is too complicated or useful for teachers, rather we believe that the most appropriate method and approach for training is based on the quality and structure of the teachers' own lessons. The optional aspect of learning is intended to help students and improve the effectiveness of the environment. Diversity and flexibility are meaningful features of the classroom setting.

The chain of modern pedagogical technologies, strategies, methods and principles in teaching English is a criterion for organizing interactive classes and the potential for interest is sufficiently developed, as a result of which the positive characteristics of the individual potential of cooperation methods are correspondingly perfected. *"Each method or method selected by the teacher not only increases the effectiveness of the lesson - training, but also increases the student's productivity, which represents the goal of being one step ahead of the teacher's goals."*². In increasing the student's scientific potential, it is focused on concretizing the goals and tasks of each principle and ensuring consistency, in which international and national cooperation strengthened the modern teaching strategy of professors and teachers and expanded the principles of experience.

In conclusion, each of the above purposefully used teaching methods helps to reveal some of the student's skills, for example, deductive and inductive learning areas develop the student's internal and external knowledge skills, creative thinking, learning and analysis. directs to methods. So, when the teacher, based on his principle, introduces the methods selected based on the purpose and principle of his planned lesson into the individual or team-style educational form, the overall revitalization, i.e. growth, is gradually strengthened. goes We, pedagogues, understand very well that we cannot limit ourselves to only one method or method in the English language class, which is a situation that puts the student in a difficult situation. It is necessary to avoid such a model of

² Penny Ur "A Course in Language Teaching: Practice of Theory "Cambridge Teacher Training and Development. 2009.p123.

homogeneity of a teacher-pedagogue and to increase the effectiveness of new competences.

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